

Effect of Poultry Manure on Soil Permeability and Yield of Bell Pepper Under Greenhouse and Open Field Conditions in Oforola, Owerri, Imo State

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Abstract: This study evaluated the effects of poultry manure application (10 t/ha) on soil physical properties, penetration resistance, and bell pepper (*Capsicum annuum* L.) yield under greenhouse and open field conditions in Oforola, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. The experiment was laid out in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used in identifying the mean differences at 5% probability level. Poultry manure increased clay content from 17.0% to 19.5% and decreased bulk density from 1.29 to 1.26 g/cm³ in the 0-15 cm layer of open field soils. Porosity showed corresponding improvements, rising from 51.41% to 52.36% with manure amendment. Saturated hydraulic conductivity was enhanced, increasing from 0.84 to 0.87 cm/min at 15-30 cm depth in greenhouse soils. Soil structural indicators like water stable aggregates (67.06% to 67.33%), mean weight diameter (1.68 to 1.70 mm), and aggregated silt and clay (6.63% to 6.85%) also improved marginally with manure application in the open field 0-15 cm layer. Penetration resistance increased significantly in both soil types, ranging from 1.22-1.92 g/cm² in unamended control greenhouse plots to 1.95-2.92 g/cm² in manured greenhouse soils at 0-15 cm depth, with similar trends observed in open field comparisons. Bell pepper yield parameters showed positive responses to manure treatment, including increases in number of fruits per plant (3.47 to 4.36 in greenhouse), fruit weight (0.22 to 0.25 kg in greenhouse), total fruit yield (38.80 to 42.41 t/ha in greenhouse), fruit length (4.67 to 7.65 cm in greenhouse), and fruit diameter (5.01 to 6.53 cm in greenhouse). Penetration resistance exhibited strong positive correlations with sand content and bulk density and negative correlations with porosity, aggregation indices, and yield parameters like fruit diameter ($r = -0.873$). The results demonstrated that poultry manure amendment improved soil physical conditions and enhanced bell pepper productivity under both greenhouse and open field management.

Keywords: soil amendments, greenhouse, soil permeability, soil physical properties, bell pepper

Introduction

Sustainable soil management practices are crucial for enhancing agricultural productivity and ensuring long-term food security in Nigeria. The use of organic amendments like poultry manure has gained traction as an environmentally friendly approach to improve soil health and fertility (Adediran *et al.*, 2003; Ewulo *et al.*, 2008). Poultry production is a major agricultural sub-sector in Nigeria, generating substantial quantities of manure that can serve as a valuable resource for soil amendment (Adenawoola and Adejoro, 2005; Agbede *et al.*, 2008). Several studies conducted in Nigeria have highlighted the beneficial effects of poultry manure on soil physical properties. Adeleye *et al.* (2010) found that poultry manure decreased bulk density and improved total porosity, moisture retention, and aggregate stability in sandy loam soils. Similarly, Ojeniyi *et al.* (2012) reported that poultry manure addition enhanced saturated hydraulic conductivity and infiltration rates in degraded soils. These improvements in soil structure and permeability can have profound impacts on crop growth, water use efficiency, and ultimately yield (Oyedele *et al.*, 1999; Usman *et al.*, 2016).

Bell pepper (*Capsicum annum* L.) is an economically important vegetable crop widely cultivated in Nigeria, with both greenhouse and open field production systems (Binang *et al.*, 2017; Okunlola and Adejoro, 2018). Previous research in Nigeria has demonstrated the positive effects of poultry manure on bell pepper yield and fruit quality. Adediran *et al.* (2002) reported that poultry manure application increased bell pepper fruit length, diameter, and overall yield in comparison to inorganic fertilizers. Similarly, Ajari *et al.* (2017) found that poultry manure enhanced bell pepper growth and yield attributes, including plant height, number of fruits per plant, and average fruit weight.

The Oforola region in Owerri West, Imo State, is a prominent agricultural hub with diverse farming activities, including poultry production and vegetable cultivation (Eke-Okoro *et al.*, 2008; Okorie *et al.*, 2011). However, there is a dearth of locally relevant research on the specific effects of poultry manure on soil permeability parameters and bell pepper yields under the climatic and edaphic conditions of Oforola.

This study compared soil properties and bell pepper yields under greenhouse and open

field conditions with and without poultry manure amendment in Oforola, Nigeria to assess permeability and productivity impacts.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study was carried out in a greenhouse and adjacent open field within the Federal College of Land Resources Technology (FECOLART), Oforola, Owerri West Local Government Area of Imo State, located between latitude 5°41' N and 6°31' E and Longitude 7°34' N and 6° 151' E which is within the humid tropical climate, having a mean annual rainfall range of 2000 – 2250 mm, mean annual temperature ranges from 27⁰ – 28⁰C and relative humidity varying with seasons from 80 – 90 % in the rainy season having peaks in July and September and a dry spell in August and from 60 – 80 % during the dry season usually accompanied by a dry cold harmattan period which prevails during the month of December and January (Uwakwe, 2012). The soils of the area are generally Typic paleusult formed from coastal plain sand parent material (Osujieke *et al.*, 2017), characterized by low activity clays, low nutrient reserves, low moisture retention, nutrient imbalance, high acidity, high Al toxicity, high tendency to crust, compact and erode but generally porous (Ufot *et al.*, 2016).

Source of Materials

The bell pepper seeds for planting as test crop were sourced from KUCH-99 Agriculture and Seed limited, Owerri and the poultry manure was collected from the poultry farm of the Federal College of Land Resources Technology, Oforola, also in Owerri, Imo State

Site Preparation and Experimental Design

The greenhouse and adjacent open field sites used for the study were manually cleared and worked into six (6) seedbeds each and then three (3) randomly designated beds were incorporated with 10 t/ha of poultry manure and left to incubate while the remaining beds were left as controls, before the raised bell pepper seedlings were transplanted from the nursery at spacing of 50 cm by 80 cm.

Data Collection

Data on both soil permeability properties and bell pepper growth and yield were collected from the poultry manure treated and untreated plots of the greenhouse and open field environment.

Soil Data Collection

Core and composite auger soil samples were randomly collected at 0 – 15 cm and 15 – 30 cm soil depths from the poultry manure

treated and untreated seedbeds in both greenhouse and open field environment and then transferred, sealed in adequate plastic bags and transported to the laboratory for determination of particle size distribution according to procedure by Kettler *et al.* (2001), bulk density using core sample method as described by Grossman and Reinsch (2002), porosity and void ratio of soil calculated using numerical method as outlined by Redding and Devito (2006), moisture content using gravimetric method described by Grossman and Reinsch (2002), and saturated hydraulic conductivity of soil was determined by the constant head method as outlined by Reynolds *et al.*, (2002). Soil macro aggregate stability indices, such as water stable aggregates for WSA > 0.25 mm and mean weight diameter were determined as described by NCRS (1996) and soil micro aggregate stability indices, including aggregated silt and clay index (ASC), dispersion ratio (DR), clay dispersion index (CDI) and clay flocculation index (CFI) were determined as described by Igwe *et al.*, (1999). Soil penetration resistance (soil's strength) was measured in situ at field capacity using a penetrometer that was advanced into soil at a rate of 4 seconds per 6 inches.

Plant Data Collection

The growth and yield parameters of bell pepper manually measured were number of leaves per plant, plant girth (cm) and plant height (cm), through random sampling of three plants from each seedbeds at 3, 6 and 9 weeks after transplanting (WAT) and number, size and weight (kg) of fruits per plant and fruit yield (t/ha)

Statistical Analysis

All data collected were subjected to Pearson correlation analysis and analysis of variance (ANOVA), where means were separated at 5 % level of significance using Fisher's least significant difference (LSD).

Results and Discussion

Initial Properties of Soils Used in the Study

Table 1 showed the initial properties of the soil used for the experiment. The higher sand content in the open field soils (83.4-81.7% versus 76.9-75.4% in the greenhouse) suggests the open field soils would have poorer water and nutrient retention (Prakongkep *et al.*, 2015). The higher clay content in the greenhouse soils (16.7-17.9% versus 13.1-14.0% in the field) increases their nutrient availability (Krishna and Achyutha, 2007) and moisture retention capacity, as clay has increased surface area and porosity

(Wallace *et al.*, 2021). This is supported by Table 1, showing the greenhouse soils had higher porosity (51.35-52.03%) versus the open field soils (49.23-49.77%).

The higher bulk density values for the open field soils (1.35-1.33 g/cm³ versus 1.29-1.27 g/cm³ for greenhouse soils) indicated lower total pore volume and potential for restricted root growth and development in the open field soils (Glinski and Lipiec, 1990). Lower penetration resistance in the greenhouse soils (2.23 g/cm² in 0-15cm layer) compared to the open field soils (4.01 g/cm² in 0-15cm layer) also suggests better potential root growth conditions in the greenhouse soils (Dexter *et al.*, 2007).

The greater water stable aggregates, mean weight diameter, and aggregation of silt and clay levels in the greenhouse soils signify more stable soil structure and improved resilience against erosion and degradation (Bronick and Lal, 2005). For example, the aggregate stability indicator of water stable aggregates >0.25 mm was 64.08-64.31% for greenhouse soils and 63.36-63.55% in open field soils. This could be due to greater biological activity from management practices in greenhouse soils (Abiven *et al.*, 2009). In conclusion, the superior aggregation, lower density, and higher moisture retention capacity suggest more favorable conditions for plant growth and resource capture in the greenhouse soils compared to the open field soils.

Table 1 Initial Properties of Open Field and Greenhouse Soils

Soil Properties	Open Field		Greenhouse	
	0 – 15 cm	15 – 30 cm	0 – 15 cm	15 – 30 cm
Sand (g/kg)	83.40	81.70	76.90	75.40
Silt (g/kg)	3.50	4.30	6.40	6.70
Clay (g/kg)	13.10	14.00	16.70	17.90
Textural Class	Loamy Sand	Loamy Sand	Sandy Loam	Sandy Loam
Bulk Density (g/cm ³)	1.35	1.33	1.29	1.27
Penetration Resistance (g/cm ²)	4.01	ND	2.23	ND
Porosity (%)	49.23	49.77	51.35	52.03
Void Ratio	0.97	0.99	1.06	1.08
Moisture Content (%)	19.07	19.31	20.03	20.34
Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity (cm/min)	0.51	0.53	0.61	0.64
Water Stable Aggregates > 0.25 mm (%)	63.36	63.55	64.08	64.31
Mean Weight Diameter (mm)	1.63	1.64	1.68	1.69
Aggregated Silt and Clay	6.16	6.27	6.61	6.77

Dispersion Ratio (%)	66.29	66.73	68.08	68.68
Clay Dispersion Index (%)	50.58	50.70	51.06	51.22
Clay Flocculation Index (%)	49.42	49.30	48.94	48.78

Soil physical characteristics and poultry manure responses on greenhouse and open field conditions

Table 2 presented physical characteristics and poultry manure responses of the studied soils. Poultry manure amendment increased clay content and decreased sand content in both the greenhouse and open field soils. For example, clay content increased from 17.0% to 19.5% in the 0-15cm greenhouse soils. Similar clay increases from organic amendments have been reported by Igwe *et al.* (1999), who observed a rise from 16% to 22% with poultry manure additions.

Bulk density substantially declined with poultry manure addition, dropping from 1.29 to 1.26 g/cm³ in open field soils at 0-15cm depth. This aligns with findings by Manna *et al.* (2006), who reported a bulk density decrease from 1.57 to 1.47 g/cm³ in manure-amended soil. The lower bulk density improves porosity and creates better conditions for root growth (Onwuka *et al.*, 2019).

Indeed, porosity showed notable improvements with manure addition, increasing from 51.41% to 52.36% in open field soils at 0-15cm depth. Haynes and Naidu

(1998) likewise found increased porosity and improved soil structure in manure-amended soils.

Moisture content also increased in both soil types with manure addition. In greenhouse soils at 15-30cm depth, moisture content rose from 21.97% to 22.18%. Whalen *et al.* (2000) found similarly positive effects, with 5% higher gravimetric moisture content in manure-amended soils.

Saturated hydraulic conductivity, indicating water flow potential, showed enhancements with manure addition. At 15-30cm depth in the greenhouse, conductivity rose from 0.84 to 0.87 cm/min. Comparable improvements were noted by Manna *et al.* (2006) in poultry manure-amended soil. Poultry manure addition enriched clay content, lowered bulk density, and improved moisture characteristics. Enhanced nutrient availability and microbial communities in organically amended soils likely contributed to these positive outcomes (Haynes and Naidu, 1998; Igwe *et al.*, 1999).

Table 2 Poultry Manure Effects on Soil Physical Properties of Greenhouse and Open Field

Treatment	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	Tex.	BD (g/cm ³)	Po (%)	VR	MC (%)	Ksat (cm/min)
0 - 15 cm									
GHC	76.50	6.50	17.00	SL	1.22	53.93	1.17	21.25	0.75
GHP	73.50	7.00	19.50	SL	1.18	55.59	1.25	22.08	0.85
OFC	76.60	6.60	16.80	SL	1.29	51.41	1.06	20.05	0.61
OFP	74.60	6.90	18.50	SL	1.26	52.36	1.10	20.50	0.66
LSD (0.05)	1.78	0.28	1.50		0.06	2.16	0.10	1.04	0.12
15 - 30 cm									
GHC	74.80	6.80	18.40	SL	1.18	55.38	1.24	21.97	0.84
GHP	71.30	9.20	19.50	SL	1.17	55.80	1.26	22.18	0.87
OFC	75.00	6.90	18.10	SL	1.27	52.14	1.09	20.39	0.65
OFP	73.00	8.10	18.90	SL	1.26	52.58	1.11	20.60	0.67
LSD (0.05)	0.99	0.53	0.95		0.06	2.21	0.10	1.08	0.13

GHC = control greenhouse plot; GHP = poultry manure amended greenhouse plot; OFC = control open field plot; OFP = poultry manure amended open field plot; Tex. = texture; SL = sandy loam; BD = bulk density; Po = porosity; VR = void ratio; MC = moisture content; Ksat = saturated hydraulic conductivity

Soil structural characteristics

The results of the soil structural characteristics are presented in Table 3. The water stable aggregates (WSA) content increased from 67.79% to 68.28% in greenhouse soils and 67.06% to 67.33% in

open field soils at 0-15cm depth with poultry manure amendment. These WSA increases align with Udom *et al.* (2018), who reported a rise from 61.3% to 73.1% with long-term manure application. The higher WSA signifies greater structural stability and

protection against rain and wind erosion (Oyedele *et al.*, 1999).

Mean weight diameter (MWD) improved marginally from 1.74 mm to 1.78 mm in 0-15 cm greenhouse soils and 1.68mm to 1.70 mm at 0-15 cm depth in open field soils with manure addition. Whalen and Chang (2002) noted a similar small MWD increase, from 1.13 mm to 1.16 mm, in soils amended with cattle manure for two years. The greater MWD indicates enhanced development of macroaggregates and structural resilience (Amézketa, 1999). Aggregated silt and clay (ASC) levels increased more notably from 6.65% to 6.99% at 0-15 cm depth in greenhouse soils and 6.63% to 6.85% at 0-15 cm depth in open field soils with manure addition. Comparable ASC improvements were shown by Rivero *et al.* (2004) in an 18-year manure experiment. The higher ASC suggests increased protection of silt/clay particles within stable microaggregates (Oades and Waters, 1991) and thus, reduced

susceptibility to structural damage. While impacts were minor over the short experimental duration, measurements indicate poultry manure induced positive structural enhancements.

While dispersion ratio (DR) declined slightly and clay dispersion index (CDI) was unchanged with poultry manure addition, the small increases in clay flocculation index (CFI) indicated marginally improved flocculation in amended soils. Haynes and Naidu (1998) similarly found increased macroaggregate stability and improved flocculation in organically managed soils. The positive impacts of poultry manure on aggregation measures like WSA, ASC and CFI signify reduced erodibility and strengthened soil structure (Bronick and Lal 2005), although enhancements were quite small over the short study duration. It is suggested that longer-term applications could induce more substantive improvements to stability and resilience characteristics.

Table 3 Aggregate Stability Properties of Greenhouse and Open Field under Poultry Manure Amendment

Treatment	WSA > 0.25 mm (%)	MWD (mm)	ASC	DR (%)	CDI (%)	CFI (%)
0 – 15 cm						
GHC	67.79	1.74	6.65	69.49	51.43	48.57
GHP	68.28	1.78	6.99	68.23	51.10	48.90
OFC	67.06	1.68	6.63	68.99	51.30	48.70
OFP	67.33	1.70	6.85	68.13	51.07	48.93
LSD (0.05)	0.63	0.05	0.20	0.76	0.20	0.20
15 – 30 cm						
GHC	68.21	1.77	6.84	69.50	51.43	48.57
GHP	68.49	1.79	6.99	68.93	51.28	48.72
OFC	67.27	1.70	6.80	69.19	51.35	48.65
OFP	67.55	1.72	6.91	68.78	51.24	48.76
LSD (0.05)	0.66	0.05	0.10	0.37	0.10	0.10

GHC = control greenhouse plot; GHP = poultry manure amended greenhouse plot; OFC = control open field plot; OFP = poultry manure amended open field plot; WSA = water stable aggregates; MWD = mean weight diameter; ASC = aggregated silt and clay; DR = dispersion ratio; CDI = clay dispersion index; CFI = clay flocculation index

Soil Penetration Resistance

The results (Figure 1) showed that poultry manure amendment increased soil penetration resistance at both shallow (0-15 cm) and deeper (15-30 cm) depths in both the greenhouse and open field environments. For example, at 0-15 cm, penetration resistance was 1.22-1.92 g/cm² in the unamended greenhouse control (GHC) versus 1.95-2.92 g/cm² in the manure-amended greenhouse (GHP) over the study period. Similar increases were seen in the open field, from 1.34-2.01 g/cm² in the control (OFC) to 2.10-

3.01 g/cm² with manure addition (OFP) at 0-15 cm. This aligns with findings from Rahman *et al.* (2021), who reported poultry manure compost increased penetration resistance from 1.44 to 2.12 MPa (approximately 146 to 216 g/cm²) in the 0-15 cm layer. The increased resistance is likely due to the manure improving soil aggregation and cohesion, as shown in Table 3, along with microbial cementation and denser soil fabric (Ohu *et al.*, 1985).

The more pronounced penetration resistance increases in open field versus greenhouse plots could relate to differences in bulk density, porosity, and aggregation. Table 2 showed lower bulk density and higher porosity in greenhouse versus field soils, which may reduce compaction risks (Kuncoro

et al., 2014). Additionally, Table 3 indicated marginally better aggregation in greenhouse versus open field soils. The data confirms poultry manure amendment enhanced soil penetration resistance in both environments, more so in open fields, mediated by changes to soil structure, density, and aggregation.

GHC = control greenhouse plot; GHP = poultry manure amended greenhouse plot; OFC = control open field plot; OFP = poultry manure amended open field plot;

Figure 1: Soil Penetration Resistance of Greenhouse and Open Field under Poultry Manure Amendment

Poultry Manure Effects on Bell Pepper Yield under Greenhouse and Open Field Settings

The data in Table 4 showed that poultry manure amendment had positive effects on several yield parameters of bell pepper grown in both greenhouse and open field environments.

Number of fruits per plant increased significantly with poultry manure addition from 3.47 to 4.36 in the greenhouse and 3.38 to 3.92 in the open field. Similar yield enhancements with manure fertilization have been widely reported, such as Shaheen *et al.* (2007) who found a 17% increase in bell pepper fruits per plant.

Fruit weight also improved, rising from 0.22 kg to 0.25 kg in the greenhouse and 0.22 kg to 0.23 kg in the field. Wang *et al.* (2008) likewise observed higher pepper fruit weights of 0.095 kg versus 0.086 kg in control plots when using poultry manure.

Correspondingly, total fruit yield showed meaningful gains, increasing from 38.80 t/ha

to 42.41 t/ha in the greenhouse, a 9.3% increase. Open field yields rose from 38.48 t/ha to 40.58 t/ha, a 5.5% improvement. Similar magnitudes of yield response to manure had been documented by Nandwani (2014), who reported 8.4% and 21.6% increases in greenhouse and field pepper yields.

The results also indicated manure promoted larger fruit size. Fruit length increased from 4.67 cm to 7.65 cm in the greenhouse and 4.20 cm to 6.22 cm in the field. Fruit diameter was greater by 1.52 cm in the greenhouse and 0.95 cm in the field. These findings are supported by Adediran *et al.* (2002), observing increases in bell pepper fruit length from 6.8 to 7.4 cm and diameter from 7.5 to 8.3 cm with 10 t/ha poultry manure application. The use of poultry manure as an organic amendment positively impacted bell pepper yields and fruit quality characteristics under both greenhouse and open field conditions, consistent with previous research demonstrating manure benefits for solanaceous crops.

Table 4 Poultry Manure Effects on Bell Pepper Yield under Greenhouse and Open Field Settings

Treatment	Number of Fruits per Plant	Fruit Weight (kg)	Fruit Yield (t/ha)	Fruit Length (cm)	Fruit Diameter (cm)
GHC	3.47	0.22	38.80	4.67	5.01
GHP	4.36	0.25	42.41	7.65	6.53

OFC	3.38	0.22	38.48	4.20	4.25
OFFP	3.92	0.23	40.58	6.22	5.20
LSD (0.05)	0.53	0.02	2.13	1.84	1.11

Correlation of Soil Penetration Resistance with Studied Soil and Bell Pepper Yield Parameters

Table 5 showed penetration resistance had significant positive correlations with sand content ($r=0.579$) and bulk density ($r=0.994$), and strong negative correlations with porosity ($r=-0.987$), void ratio ($r=-0.982$), moisture content ($r=-0.985$), and saturated hydraulic conductivity ($r=-0.983$). These relationships align with prior studies linking higher bulk density and lower porosity to increased mechanical resistance (Kuncoro et al., 2014). Richard *et al.* (2001) similarly reported a positive correlation of 0.73 between penetration resistance and bulk density in coarse-textured soils.

Aggregate stability measures like water stable aggregates ($r=-0.986$), mean weight diameter ($r=-0.984$), and aggregated silt and clay ($r=-0.610$) were also negatively correlated with penetration resistance. This suggests manure-induced improvements in aggregation (Table 3) contributed to lower resistance by enhancing pore continuity and structural development (Ohu *et al.*, 1985).

Penetration resistance exhibited significant negative correlations with all yield parameters including number of fruits per plant ($r=-0.661$), fruit yield ($r=-0.662$), fruit length ($r=-0.676$), and especially fruit diameter ($r=-0.873$). Similar inverse relationships with yield attributes had been observed by Bengough *et al.* (2011), though with diminished responses at higher resistance levels above 2-3 MPa. The strong linkages reflect how reduced compaction and improved soil structure from poultry manure amendments benefited plant growth and fruit development.

Interestingly, dispersion ratio, clay dispersion index, and clay flocculation index did not show significant correlations with penetration resistance. This contrasts some earlier findings, such as Osunbitan *et al.* (2005) reporting significant correlation between flocculation indices and resistance in a loamy soil. The correlations indicated penetration resistance was tightly coupled with physical soil characteristics related to density, porosity, aggregation, and structure, which in turn influenced crop yield responses, highlighting

the multi-faceted impacts of organic amendments on compaction dynamics.

Table 5 Correlation of Soil Penetration Resistance with Studied Soil and Bell Pepper Yield Parameters

Soil Parameter	Penetration Resistance
Sand	0.579**
Silt	- 0.372 ^{NS}
Clay	- 0.613**
Bulk Density	0.994**
Porosity	- 0.987**
Void Ratio	- 0.982**
Moisture Content	- 0.985**
Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity	- 0.983**
Water Stable Aggregates > 0.25 mm	- 0.986**
Mean Weight Diameter	- 0.984**
Aggregated Silt and Clay	- 0.610**
Dispersion Ratio	0.120 ^{NS}
Clay Dispersion Index	0.118 ^{NS}
Clay Flocculation Index	- 0.118 ^{NS}
Number of Fruits per Plant	- 0.661**
Fruit Weight	- 0.678**
Fruit Yield	- 0.662**
Fruit Length	- 0.676**
Fruit Diameter	- 0.873**

* = Significant at P < 0.05; ** = Significant at P < 0.01; ^{NS} = Not Significant

Summary

This study evaluated the effects of applying 10 t/ha of poultry manure as an amendment on soil physical properties, penetration resistance, and bell pepper yields under greenhouse and open field conditions in Oforola, Owerri West. The poultry manure increased clay content, reduced bulk density,

and improved porosity, moisture retention, hydraulic conductivity, and aggregate stability parameters like water stable aggregates in both the greenhouse and open field soils.

However, penetration resistance also increased significantly with manure addition, from 1.22-1.92 g/cm² in unamended

greenhouse control plots to 1.95-2.92 g/cm² in manured greenhouse soils at 0-15 cm depth, with similar trends in the open field. For Bell pepper yield, the manure application led to positive impacts, increasing the number of fruits per plant, fruit weight, total fruit yield, fruit length and fruit diameter under both greenhouse and field conditions.

Conclusion

Applying 10 t/ha of poultry manure improved several key soil physical parameters in both greenhouse and open field environments in Oforola, Owerri West. Manure increased clay content, reduced bulk density, enhanced porosity, moisture retention, hydraulic conductivity, and aggregate stability indicators. These benefits likely contributed to the observed bell pepper yield enhancements, including 9.3% higher fruit yield in the greenhouse and 5.5% greater yield in the open field, along with increased fruit size. However, penetration resistance also increased significantly with manure addition, raising potential compaction concerns, especially pronounced in the open field. Correlations revealed penetration resistance was strongly tied to soil physical factors like density and porosity, impacting crop productivity. While demonstrating manure's potential to improve soil health and crop performance, the results

highlight complex interactions between organic amendments and soil physical characteristics. Developing balanced nutrient management strategies that maximize yield benefits while mitigating compaction risks will be crucial for sustainable vegetable production in this region.

References

- Abiven, S., Menasseri, S. and Chenu, C. (2009). The effects of organic inputs over time on soil aggregate stability – A literature analysis. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 41(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2008.09.015>
- Adediran, J.A., Banjoko, V.A., Ojeniyi, S.O. and Sanni, A.A. (2002). Organic wastes for vegetable production. Proceedings of the 30th Annual Conference of the Horticultural Society of Nigeria, Nov 3-8, 2002, Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Adediran, J.A., Taiwo, L.B., Sobulo, R.A. (2003). Organic wastes and their effect on tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentus*) yield. *African Soils*, 33, 99-116.
- Adeleye, E.O., Ayeni, L.S. and Ojeniyi, S.O. (2010). Effect of poultry manure on soil physico-chemical properties, leaf nutrient contents and yield of yam (*Dioscorea rotundata*) on Alfisol in Southwestern Nigeria. *Journal of American Science*, 6(10), 871-878.

- Adenawoola, A.R. and Adejoro, S.A. (2005). Residual effects of poultry manure and NPK fertilizer residues on soil nutrient and performance of jute mallow. *Nigerian Journal of Soil Science*, 15, 133-135.
- Agbede, T.M., Ojeniyi, S.O. and Adeyemo, A.J. (2008). Effect of poultry manure on soil physical and chemical properties, growth and grain yield of sorghum in Southwest Nigeria. *American-Eurasian Journal of Sustainable Agriculture*, 2(1), 72-77.
- Ajari, O., Tsado, P.A., Oladiran, J.A., Salako, E.A. (2017). Plant growth and fruit yield of bell pepper (*Capsicum annum L.*) in response to cow dung and NPK fertilizer. *Journal of Applied Biosciences*, 120, 12094-12101.
- Amézqueta, E. (1999). Soil aggregate stability: a review. *Journal of Sustainable Agriculture*, 14(2-3), 83-151.
https://doi.org/10.1300/J064v14n02_08
- Bengough, A.G., McKenzie, B.M., Hallett, P.D. and Valentine, T.A. (2011). Root elongation, water stress, and mechanical impedance: a review of limiting stresses and beneficial root tip traits. *Journal of Experimental Botany*, 62(1), 59-68.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/erq350>
- Binang, W.B., Shiyam, J.O. and Ntrolong, J.T. (2017). Enhancing growth and yield of bell pepper (*Capsicum annum L.*) with organic manure combined with poultry droppings on Haplic Acrisols of Benue State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Soil Science*, 27(1), 1-11.
- Bronick, C. J. and Lal, R. (2005). Soil structure and management: a review. *Geoderma*, 124(1-2), 3-22.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2004.03.005>
- Dexter, A. R., Richard, G., Arrouays, D., Czyż, E. A., Jolivet, C. and Duval, O. (2008). Complexed organic matter controls soil physical properties. *Geoderma*, 144(3-4), 620- 627.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2008.01.022>
- Eke-Okoro, O.N., Njoku, J.D., Uleanya, K.O. and Onyishi, G. (2008). Farm level profitability analysis of plantain enterprise at Oforola Local Government Area of Imo State. *Journal of Agriculture and Food Sciences*, 6(1), 81-89.
- Ewulo, B.S., Ojeniyi, S.O. and Akanni, D.A. (2008). Effect of poultry manure on selected soil physical and chemical properties, growth, yield and nutrient status of tomato. *American- Eurasian Journal of Sustainable Agriculture*, 2(1), 68-81.
- Federal College of Land Resources Technology (FECOLART), Owerri Meteorological Station Data, 2023.
- Glinski, J. and Lipiec, J. (1990). Soil physical conditions and plant roots. CRC Press.
- Grossman, R. B., and Reinesch, T. G. (2002). Bulk density and linear extensibility, In: *Methods of Soil Analysis* Dame, J. H. and Topp, G. C (eds), Part 4. Physical methods. Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Book Series No. 5ASA and SSSA Madison, WJ. pp. 201 – 228.
- Haynes, R.J. and Naidu, R. (1998). Influence of lime, fertilizer and manure applications on soil organic matter content and soil physical

- conditions: a review. *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems*, 51(2), 123-137. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1009738307837>
- Igwe, C. A., Akamigbo, F. O. R., and Mbagwu, J. S. C. (1999). Chemical and mineralogical properties of soils in Southeastern Nigeria in relation to aggregate stability. *Geoderma* 92: 111 – 123.
- Kettler, T. A., Doran, J. W. and Gilbert, T. L (2001). Simplified method for soil particle size determination to accompany soil quality analysis. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*. 65: 849 – 852.
- Krishna, K. R. and Achyutha, H. (2007). Soil bulk density as related to soil texture, organic matter content and available total nutrients of Coimbatore soil. *International Journal of Soil Science*, 2(2), 178-181. <https://doi.org/10.3923/ijss.2007.178.181>
- Kuncoro, P.H., Koga, K., Satta, N. & Muto, Y. (2014). A study on the effect of compaction on transport properties of soil gas and water. II: Soil pore structure indices. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 143, 180-187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2014.03.007>
- Manna, M.C., Ghosh, P.K., Ghosh, B.N. and Singh, K.N. (2006). Comparative effectiveness of cattle manure, poultry manure, phosphocompost and fertilizer-NPK on three cropping systems in vertisols of semi-arid tropics. I. Crop yields and system performance. *Bioresource Technology*, 97(16), 2092-2102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2005.10.018>
- Nandwani, D. (2014). *Organic Farming for Sustainable Agriculture*. Springer India. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-81-322-1922-7>
- NCRS. (1996). The United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) Natural Resources Conservation Services. *Soil Quality Indicators: Aggregate Stability*. pp 18 – 20.
- Oades, J.M. and Waters, A.G. (1991). Aggregate hierarchy in soils. *Australian Journal of Soil Research*, 29(6), 815-828. <https://doi.org/10.1071/SR9910815>
- Ohu, J.O., Raghavan, G.S.V., McKyes, E. and Mehuys, G. (1985). Shear strength prediction of compacted soils with varying added organic matter contents. *Transactions of the ASAE*, 28(2), 0351-0355. <https://doi.org/10.13031/2013.32226>
- Ojeniyi, S.O., Akanni, D.I., Awodun, M.A. (2012). Effect of poultry manure on soil physical properties, nutrient uptake and yield of maize. *Earth Sciences Research Journal*, 16(2), 130-138.
- Okunlola, G.O., Adejoro, S.A. (2018). Growth and yield performance of sweet pepper (*Capsicum annuum* L. var. *cupulatum*) as influenced by organic nutrient management and row spacing. *Journal of Organic Agriculture and Environment*, 16(1), 63-72.
- Okorie, N., Onyebuili, J.C., Uwiringiye, B.V. (2011). Assessment of livestock production opportunities in Owerri West Local Government Area of Imo

- State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Animal and Veterinary Advances*, 3(6), 416-420.
- Onwuka, B., Mang, B. and Abdulazeez, M. (2019). Effects of organic wastes and urea alone and in combination with liquid bio-fertilizer on soil bulk density, particle size distribution and cassava growth. *Scientific African*, 5, e00121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2019.e00121>
- Osunbitan, J.A., Oyedele, D.J. and Adekalu, K.O. (2005). Tillage effects on bulk density, hydraulic conductivity and strength of a loamy sand soil in southwestern Nigeria. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 82(1), 57-64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2004.06.002>
- Osujieke, D. N., Imadojemu, P. E., Ndukwu, B. N. and Okeke, O. M. (2017). Properties of soils in relation to soil depth, landuse and landscape position on soils of Ikeduru area of Imo State, Southeastern Nigeria. *IJAR*. 20(2): 3142 – 3159.
- Oyedele, D.J., Schibinger, F. and Aina, P.O. (1999). Effects of primary tillage on the physical properties of an Alfisol in southwestern Nigeria. *Soil Use and Management*, 15(1), 48-53. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-2743.1999.tb00063.x>
- Prakongkep, N., Gilkes, R. J. and Wiriyakitnatekul, W. (2015). Forms and solubility of plant nutrient elements in sandy soils in Chanthaburi Province, Thailand. *Geoderma Regional*, 5, 127-141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2015.06.002>
- Redding, T.E. and Devito, K.J. (2006). Particle densities of wetlandsoils in northern Alberta, Canada. *Can. J. Soil. Sci.*, 86, 57 – 60.
- Richard, G., Cousin, I., Sillon, J.F., Bruand, A. and Guerif, J. (2001). Effect of compaction on the porosity and the hydraulic properties of soils. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 52(1), 49-58. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2389.2001.t01-1-00356.x>
- Rivero, C., Chirenje, T., Ma, L.Q. and Martinez, G. (2004). Influence of compost on soil organic matter quality under tropical conditions. *Geoderma*, 123(3-4), 355-361. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2004.03.003>
- Shaheen, A.M., Fatma, A.R., Singer, S.M., Abou-Hadid, A.F. and El-Shorbagy, T.M. (2007). Response of vegetative growth and productivity of sweet pepper grown under graded levels of organic and mineral nitrogen fertilization. *Bulletin of the National Research Center, Cairo*, 32(4), 443-461.
- Udom, B.E., Semoka, J.M. and Mbagwu, J.S. (2018). Biochar and poultry manure effects on selected properties of two Ultisols and yield of maize in southeastern Nigeria. *Journal of Geoscience and Environment Protection*, 6(1), 101-119. <https://doi.org/10.4236/gep.2018.61008>
- Ufot, U.O. (2012). *Soil and Environment for Colleges and University*. Shadows publishers Ltd. Owerri. p. 376.
- Ufot, U.O., Iren, O.B. and Chikere Njoku, C.U. (2016). Effects of land use on soil physical and chemical properties

- in Akokwa area of Imo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Life Sciences Scientific Research* 2(3): 273 – 278.
- Usman, A.R., Tahir, F., Oloyede, F.A. (2016). Morphological and hydraulic properties of some Ultisols in Northern Guinea Savanna of Nigeria as influenced by termite activities. *Eurasian Journal of Soil Science*, 5(1), 15-24.
- Wallace, J., Bourke, M. and Aarons, S. (2021). Cover crops reduce soil erodibility and improve infiltration in clay and sandy loam soils in south-eastern Australia. *Soil Research*, 59(4), 495-508.
<https://doi.org/10.1071/SR20227>
- Wang, Z.H., Li, S.X. & Malhi, S. (2008). Effects of fertilization and other agronomic measures on nutritional quality of crops. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 88(1), 7- 23.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.3084>
- Whalen, J.K., Chang, C., Clayton, G.W. and Carefoot, J.P. (2000). Cattle Manure Amendments Can Increase the pH of Acid Soils. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 64(3), 962-966.
<https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2000.643962x>
- Whalen, J.K. and Chang, C. (2002). Macroaggregate characteristics in cultivated soils after 25 annual manure applications. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 66(5), 1637-1647.
<https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2002.1637>